

SOCIOLOGY LEARNING IN THE ERA OF DIGITALIZATION: LITERATURE REVIEW OF NEEDS, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

The contemporary digital era makes it easy for people to communicate ideas. This has an impact on education as a whole, especially on learning history in schools. For the sociology learning process to be successful, it must adapt to technological advances in the contemporary digital world. This study looks at the growth of interactive media toward the demands of sociology education in the digital era. The research library approach is used to review the methods used in published research from various related papers, journals, and books related to this writing. The findings of the need for information about sociology learning strategies in the digitalization era, through various interactive learning multimedia developments, are very important to support sociology learning and increase student competency in the digital era. Educators are also provided with socialization, information, and training to help them create up-to-date learning materials in facing the challenges of sociology learning in the digitalization era, to produce sociology learning plans or designs through learning using the blended learning model so that sociology learning can be meaningful and effective for students as the nation's successors, further studies and research are needed comprehensive and sustainable.

Keyword: Sociology Learning, Interactive Multimedia, Digitalization Era, Challenges, Opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

We have now entered a period that is marked by the advancement of information and technology [1]. To generate students who are competent by integrating the roles of schools and teachers in their learning, education must be able to adapt to education in the digital age [2]. If students and teachers wish to share knowledge throughout the learning process, they do not necessarily need to be face-to-face; instead, they can use other technology as a message delivery medium [3]. Because it already uses telecommunications tools like mobile phones and computers, and because the transmission media can send information that has been digitalized or what is known as digital information, it can save time and effort when interacting [4].

In the current learning process that needs to be considered how learning is easily accepted and interesting to be studied by students. Sociology learning is a branch of scientific discipline developed by the community by conducting research on human behavior. Sociology learning has a very important role in building the character of students [5]. In addition, learning Sociology also contributes to overcoming conflicts that occur in the ethnicity of a nation [6].

Therefore knowledge must contain wisdom values that are useful for training intelligence, forming attitudes, character and personality of students. So that through learning Sociology students can learn the values of community life and it is hoped that students can make a selection of complex values that develop in society in the present and in the future [7]. The position of Sociology learning positions shows an important role in fostering students as the young generation who will continue the nation [8].

The implementation and meaning of Sociology learning is still often misunderstood by most people at this time [9]. The problems of learning Sociology from the past until now cannot be separated from conventional learning [8]. Sociology learning that is rote does not associate character values in it so that it creates pragmatic practical thinking habits. Learning outcomes are an indicator to be able to see the quality and quantity of students [10]. Many of the problems currently faced by Sociology learning include weak use of theory, poor imagination, textbook references and state-oriented curricula, low motivation and interest of students and tendencies to be indifferent to the phenomenon of globalization [11].

Sociology learning should not only be able to build character in understanding the value contained in phenomena but must also be at the level of seeing the other side that is deep, namely technological developments so that Sociology learning is able to answer the challenge of an unavoidable change. This is due to the current development of information technology, which makes it easier for science to be more flexible in penetrating the dimensions of space and time [12]. The conventional learning paradigm using learning methods and media so far needs to be changed into innovative Sociology learning in accordance with the current digital era [13]. The use of learning media basically aims to channel messages, stimulate thoughts, feelings, attention, increase student enthusiasm and interest so that the learning process becomes more effective and efficient [14].

Therefore, what are the sociology learning strategies in the digitalization era where the ability of technology to access information that is not limited by space and time is a feature of the digital era. The digital era greatly influences human life in various aspects of life, one of which is education. In essence, education is a conscious effort to develop the potential of students by encouraging and providing facilities in the teaching and learning process.

METHOD

This type of research is descriptive research that aims to provide a clear picture of the characteristics of the phenomenon being studied. The research method used is library research to obtain various information related to sociology learning in the digitalization era by using reading techniques. Literature research methods to identify, review, evaluate and interpret all existing research [15]. This method for structured review and identification of journals follows established procedures for each process [16]. Information is collected by reading literature related to the topic being discussed. Data sources, especially literature, can be in the form of books, scientific articles, research journals, research reports, seminar papers, and other forms related to this research. The resulting data source is indexed published journals in the Google Scholar database.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Literature review

Learning Concept

Learning is essentially a process of interaction between students and students, students with the environment and students with educators. Learning activities will be meaningful for children if carried out in a comfortable and safe environment. The learning process is individual and contextual. Thus it is important for educators to learn

and add insight into learning. Learning is a process of interaction between students and educators and learning resources in a learning environment. Learning is assistance provided by educators so that the process of acquiring knowledge and knowledge can occur as well as forming attitudes and beliefs in students [17]. Learning or teaching according to Degeng is an effort to teach students. In this sense implicitly in learning there are activities of selecting, determining, and developing methods to achieve the desired learning outcomes [18]. Teori belajar Gagne mendefinisikan belajar sebagai menyusun peristiwa secara hati-hati dengan maksud agar belajar terjadi dan menjadikannya efektif [19]. In another sense, Winkel defines learning as setting and creating external conditions in such a way as to support student learning and not hinder it [20].

According to Gagne Learning is a set of external events designed to support several internal learning processes. Gagne further put forward a more complete definition of learning: instruction is intended to promote learning, external situations need to be arranged to activate support and maintain the internal processing that constitutes each learning event [19]. Learning is intended to produce learning, external situations must be designed in such a way as to activate, support and maintain the internal processes contained in each learning event [21]. The learning process can occur at any time regardless of whether someone is teaching or not. The learning process occurs because of the interaction of individuals with their environment. Because of that the term "teaching", learning is an effort that is carried out intentionally, directed and planned with goals that have been applied first before the process is carried out, and the implementation is controlled with the intention of being optimal in the process of learning objectives. Learning can also be said to be a process of transforming knowledge, because in learning there is a process of interaction between educators and students who previously did not know to know. In other words, learning is a process to help students learn well.

Everyone experiences lifelong learning and can apply anywhere and anytime. Learning has a similar meaning to teaching, although it has a different connotation. In the context of education, teachers teach so that students can learn and master the content of the lesson until they achieve a certain objective (cognitive aspect), can also influence changes in attitudes (affective aspects) and skills (psychomotor aspects) of a student. Teaching gives the impression that it is only the work of one party, namely the work of the teacher. While learning also implies an interaction between teachers and students.

Sociology Learning Concept

In terminology, sociology comes from Latin and Greek, namely the words socius and logos. socius (Greek) which means friend, comrade, or social. Logos means knowledge or can also talk about something. Thus literally the term sociology can be interpreted as the science of society. According to Pitirim Solokin said that sociology is a science that studies the relationship and mutual influence between various kinds of social phenomena, for example, family symptoms and morals or social movement and politics. By its nature and essence, sociology is a social science and not a natural science or a science of spirituality. Sociology is also an abstract science and not a concrete science, meaning that what it pays attention to are the forms and patterns of events in society but not their concrete forms [22].

The term Sociology as a branch of Social Science was first coined by a French scientist, named August Comte (later known as the Father of Sociology). Comte argued that sociology must be based on objective facts (not hopes, predictions, or predictions). There are several views of the figures regarding sociology. 1) Roucek and Warren argue that sociology is a science that studies the relationship between humans in groups, 2) William F. Ogburn and Meyer F. Nimkoff argue that sociology is scientific research on social interaction, and the result is a social organization [23].

Small put forward the notion of sociology as a social interest which stated that interests were in the hands of individuals and groups and could be categorized into issues such as health, wealth, knowledge, beauty, truth and so on. Society is considered as its interests [24]. Meanwhile, Max Weber in the book (Introduction to Sociology: 3) reveals that sociology is the study of social action. An action can be called a social action if the action is carried out by considering the behavior of others.

Humans as individual beings are not able to live alone, in their lives they will always be together and depend on other humans. This is because humans cannot fulfill their own needs in meeting their needs. In Aristotle's view, humans are zoon political, meaning that humans are creatures that always want to get along with one another, so humans are called social beings [25]. From the several opinions above, it can be concluded that sociology is a general science, because sociology only studies the symptoms that exist in every interaction between humans in a society.

Sociology is not a fixed science but a dynamic science as time goes by because every second, every minute, and every hour of social movement will always change. In social life, humans are always interdependent on one another. The object of sociology is a society in relations and also the processes resulting from these relations. The purpose of sociology is to improve a person's ability to adapt or adapt to his social environment. The subject matter of sociology is like social reality or facts, social action, sociological imagination, and disclosure of social reality.

Digitalization Learning Concept

Digital learning includes aspects of hardware (infrastructure) in the form of a set of computers that are interconnected with each other and can transmit data, whether in the form of text, messages, graphics, video, or audio [26]. With this capability, digital learning can be interpreted as a computer network that is interconnected with other computer networks throughout the world.

Digital learning is a form of information technology that is applied in the field of education in the form of virtual worlds or it can also be called E-learning learning [27]. The term digital learning is more precisely intended as an attempt to make a transformation of the learning process in schools or colleges into a digital form that is bridged by Internet technology [28].

Digital learning can also be interpreted as a learning process that is passed through a network (computer network), which is usually via the internet or intranet [29]. With internet facilities, digital learning is not continuously dependent on the teacher, because access to information (knowledge) is broader and more complete, so students can learn anytime and anywhere. Digital learning is a system that can facilitate learners to be able to learn more broadly, more, and variedly. The learning material studied is more varied, not only in verbal form, but also in text, visual, audio, and motion.

There are 3 potential digital learning that can be utilized in everyday life, namely as a communication tool, information access tool, and educational or learning tool [30] a). Potential Communication Tools By using digital learning, you can communicate anywhere quickly. For example, you can communicate using email, or discuss via chat or mailing list, b).

Potential Information Access Through digital learning, various information can be accessed, such as weather forecasts, and economic, social, political, cultural, scientific and technological developments presented by various sources without having to subscribe and, c). Potential for Education and Learning The rapid development of digital learning technology that reaches all corners of the world has been utilized by many countries, institutions and experts for various purposes including education and learning.

DISCUSSION

The learning process that emphasizes the practice of Sociology certainly requires a special learning approach. One important thing that needs to be emphasized in the sociology learning process is that the learning that is carried out does not only introduce Sociological knowledge in the abstract and memorizes concepts or theories as usual. On the other hand, it places more emphasis on the dimensions of affection or students' sensitivity and concern for the social problems they face by using sociology to solve social problems. The knowledge referred to here can refer to the sociology learning approach. In applying several strategies to learning sociology, in general, a sociology teacher has difficulty presenting sociology material topics into strategies for learning activities in the classroom so the impact of learning contributions on learning behavior in society is not optimal [31].

Some previous research on sociology learning strategies in the era of digitalization today's blended learning topics are widely studied by various groups because they are considered capable of overcoming the weaknesses that arise in face-to-face learning and online learning (e-learning). In sociology learning, in particular, studies on blended learning have been carried out a lot.

Starting from the teacher empowerment model in sociology learning based on blended learning [32]; learning media for blended learning [33]; students' perception and acceptance of blended learning [34]; comparison of blended learning with lectures [35]; as well as the effectiveness of blended learning in learning [36]. However, studies or research on how to design sociology learning with blended learning so that it is meaningful and effective for the next generation have not been studied much.

To produce sociology learning plans or designs with blended learning so that they are meaningful and effective for the nation's next generation in facing the digitalization era, comprehensive and continuous studies and research are needed. Some alternatives that can be done are to conduct research through an R and D (Research and Development) scheme to obtain a model that can be used as a reference for educators in the field in implementing blended learning or, finding good practices (best practices) related to blended learning in sociology learning in SMA which has been carried out by practitioners (teachers).

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of the needs of several previous reports in dealing with the challenges of sociology learning in the digitalization era, to produce sociology learning plans or designs through learning using a blended learning model so that sociology learning can be meaningful and effective for students as the nation's successors, further studies and research are needed. comprehensive and sustainable. Several alternatives that can be done are to conduct research through an R and D (Research and Development) scheme to obtain a model that can be used as a reference for educators in the field in implementing blended learning. Or, find good practices (best practices) related to blended learning in sociology learning in high schools that have been carried out by practitioners (teachers).

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